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Title: Commonly used herbicides with anti-thyroid activity: A brief review

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Abstract

Occupational and environmental exposure to certain herbicides have been associated with thyroid-disrupting properties, particularly changes in the thyroid hormones (T3 and T4) and thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH). Commonly used herbicides such as glyphosate (G), and paraquat (PQ) were reviewed to have thyroid-disrupting properties and can be considered as thyroid-disrupting chemicals (TDCs). On the other hand, atrazine (ATR) do not exert any impact on thyroid histology any thyroid hormones (THs). From the epidemiological, and in vivo studies it can be summarized that G, and PQ are associated with the endocrine system, particularly with thyroid hormone homeostasis. Primarily, hypothyroidism is the most prevalent condition associated with exposure to these herbicides. Neurogenesis, energy metabolism, and metamorphosis in the amphibian species-related effects are witnessed so far closely associated with G and PQ exposure.

Keywords: Atrazine; Endocrine-disrupting Chemical; Glyphosate; Herbicide; Paraquat; Thyroid.

1. Introduction

Diseases associated with the thyroid gland are among the most medically prevalent conditions, especially among females ([Garg and Vanderpump, 2013](#)). Thyroid disorders lead to affected metabolism and disability in the body composition, causing morbidity and disability in people worldwide. Thyroid homeostasis, a controlled manner of thyroid hormones (THs) synthesis and secretion is important for normal functioning. If thyroid homeostasis is disturbed, various hyperthyroidism or hypothyroidism-associated diseases such as neurological disorders and alteration in the neurodevelopment may occur ([OPP, 2005](#)). Common risk factors of thyroid disorders include female sex, aging, autoimmunity, goiter, iodine deficiency, radiation, and certain chemicals or medicines that interfere with thyroid hormone action ([Baskin et al., 2002](#); [Taylor et al., 2018](#)). Epidemiological, In vivo, and in vitro studies have identified various chemicals, at environmentally relevant concentration, can disrupt the thyroid glands normal functioning and cause deleterious health effects. These chemicals are called endocrine-disrupting chemicals which can interfere with thyroid hormone biosynthesis (iodine uptake and organification), transport, metabolism, and transport across the cell membrane, and interact with intracellular receptors ([Gore et al., 2015](#)).

This review aims to give a brief overview of the effects of herbicides particularly glyphosate, paraquat, and atrazine on the thyroid gland.

A. Herbicides

Herbicides are some chemicals used to reduce the unwanted vegetation (weeds) in agriculture, forest, and wildland ecosystems. In the agriculture ecosystem, herbicides reduce the population of weed species and promote growth to crop plants. Foreign/exotic/invasive species invading forest and wildland ecosystems can also be controlled by using specific herbicides.

Herbicides are used to kill plants or to impair the normal growth process. Sinox, developed in France in 1896 was the first major organic chemical herbicide. In the late 1940s, during World War II, new herbicides were developed out of the research, and the era of the “miracle” weed killers began. Surprisingly about 150 herbicide active ingredients are formulated into hundreds of commercial products ([Senseman, 2007](#)). Herbicides are often classified according to their chemical similarities, to some level, not always, similarities in the effect on plants. Glyphosate, paraquat, and atrazine are some of the widely used herbicides, of these glyphosate is the most widely used herbicide worldwide ([Valavandis, 2018](#)).

Most human/ animal health problems that result from exposure to herbicides are due to their improper use or careless disposal of containers ([Gupta, 2018](#)). However, there is increased concern of herbicides toxicity due to agriculture runoff, leaching to groundwater, and entrance to the drinking water system ([Lucas et al., 2019](#)). Case studies

and laboratory experiments have been conducted to know the possible endocrine effects of different herbicides used on daily basis and the results were striking.

B. Endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDCs)

The endocrine system is a network of glands and organs that produces, stores, and secret hormones. Proper functioning of the endocrine system is important to carry normal development and functioning of the body. Endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDCs) are exogenous substances that interfere with the normal functioning of this system and hormone action, and are also known as endocrine disruptors. According to a report by [Colborn and Clement \(1992\)](#), the term endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDCs) was coined by scientists at Conference in Wisconsin during the early 1990s. "WHO defines endocrine-disrupting chemical, is an exogenous substance or mixture that alters the function of the endocrine system and consequently causes adverse health effects to the intact organism, or its progeny, or (sub) populations"([Derbre, 2021](#)). EDCs have been classified as, for instance, chloro-organic pesticides, herbicides, bisphenols, phthalates, as well as parabens ([Włodarczyk-Makula, 2024](#)). Herbicides, such as linuron, 2, 4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2, 4-D), 2, 4, 5-Trichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2, 4, 5-T), alachlor (ALA), amitrol, atrazine (ATR), metribuzin, trifluraline (TRI), nitrofen, glyphosate (G), glufosinate (GA), paraquat (PQ), etc. also have endocrine-disrupting property ([Włodarczyk-Makula, 2024](#)). EDCs can modulate the endocrine functioning on different levels. Binding nuclear receptors as ligands, EDCs act like their agonist or antagonist. Till now, their impact on glucocorticoid receptors (GRs), mineralocorticoid receptors (MRs), estrogen receptors (ERs), androgen receptors (ARs), progesterone receptors (PRs), thyroid receptors (TRs), peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPARs), and aryl hydrocarbon receptors (AhRs), have been discussed ([Giulivoa et al., 2016](#)). EDCs cause the disturbance of the peripheral activity of the transported hormones after binding with plasma proteins ([Nowak et al., 2019](#)). Moreover, EDCs impair the enzymatic activity of hormones that metabolize endogenous hormones, such as aromatase, 5-reductase, 3-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase (3-HSD), and 11-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenases (11-HSDs). Furthermore, EDCs can disrupt the biosynthesis and biotransformation of natural hormones ([Giulivo et al., 2016](#)). Nevertheless, it is under consideration that in endocrine system functioning, particularly during the early developmental period can lead to extreme and lasting effects.

C. Hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid (HPT) axis: an overview

It has been the last three decades since when the roll of thyroid hormones (THs) in different biological

organizations and physiological functions were studied extensively. In humans, THs are very essential in the development of certain organs and for energy metabolism. THs are very crucial for normal brain development, which is dramatically illustrated by cretinism, a syndrome, induced due to severe lack of TH or iodine during embryo-foetal and postnatal development (PND) ([Bernal, 2007](#)). Moreover, disruption at any point of hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid (HPT) axis specifically during a crucial developmental period, particularly during pregnancy, ([Bellanger et al., 2015](#)) can lead to deleterious effects on the offspring.

To summarize, THs production and physiology vary succinctly. THs synthesis in the thyroid colloid requires iodine, which circulates in the form of iodine ion. To produce thyroxine (T4) and triiodothyronine (T3), iodide combines with amino acid tyrosine. HPT axis mainly controls the synthesis and secretion of THs (T3 and T4). The hypothalamus produces the thyrotropin-releasing hormone (TRH), which triggers the production of Thyroid-stimulation hormone (TSH) from the anterior pituitary. TSH binds to receptors on thyroid follicular cells of the thyroid gland. TSH through sodium/iodide symporter (NIS) stimulates iodide uptake. After oxidation of iodide by thyroperoxidase (TPO), iodide is incorporated into thyroglobulin (Tg), known as organification of iodide, is required to produce precursors of T3 and T4 ([Sellitti and Suzuki, 2013](#)). THs apply negative feedback on their upstream regulators thereby controlling hormone levels. Increases in T3/ T4 inhibit the production of TSH and TRH by the pituitary and hypothalamus, respectively. Inversely, when T3 and T4 decrease, TSH and TRH genes are activated ([Rousset et al., 2015](#)).

2. Paraquata

Paraquat (PQ), which is generally used for controlling the broad leave grass is one of the most widely used herbicides. PQ has caused many deaths either accidentally or after its deliberate ingestion. PQ is responsible for damage to human and animal internal organs ([Hironobu et al., 1978](#)). The thyroid gland is one of the target glands of paraquat poisoning.

A. Epidemiological evidence

Epidemiological evidence from multiple studies supports the role of paraquat as a thyroid disrupting chemical. Research has shown that paraquat exposure is associated with an increased risk of hypothyroidism ([Goldner et al., 2010](#)), and it has been linked to thyroid cancer in residential pesticide exposure studies ([Omidakhsh et al., 2022](#)).

On September 25, 1975, in a suicide case, a 47-year-old woman swallowed approximately 30 ml of undiluted paraquat (PQ). From autopsy and microscopic study, the most remarkable finding was numerous thrombi in the vessels of various sizes in the thyroid gland, and various other internal organs/glands ([Hironobu et al., 1978](#)).

[Tsatsakis et al. \(1996\)](#) reported that postmortem analysis of humans with PQ poisoning revealed detectable amounts of PQ (64µgm/gm) in the thyroid gland. They suggested that the thyroid could be susceptible to PQ ([Tsatsakis et al., 1996](#)). Analysis of the PQ intoxicated people showed a measurable amount of PQ in their thyroid glands, which was higher in women compared to men ([Steenland et al., 1997](#)) indicates there is a relationship between thyroid gland and PQ herbicide and female susceptibility. Goldner et al. (2010, 2013) observed a significant association between ever using PQ and self-reported hypothyroidism among women in the U.S. Agricultural Health Study (AHS) between 1993- 1997, but they did not find an association between self-reported use of PQ and hypothyroidism in male private pesticide applicators ([Goldner et al., 2010, 2013](#)). Kongtip et al. have shown that PQ has a significant relationship between the amount applied and thyroid hormone levels and also may have contributed to the observed cases of dysthyroidism ([Kongtip et al., 2019](#)). Further Kongtip et al. in 2021 have reported an increase in one unit of urinary PQ from the morning before to the morning after spraying among Thai farmers and found FT3 (free T3) and T3 are reduced significantly. These findings suggest that repeated acute exposure to PQ could result in chronic disequilibrium of the HPT axis and hypothyroidism, which may lead to associated metabolic disorders ([Kongtip et al., 2021](#)).

B. In vivo evidence

In vivo studies have primarily focused on paraquat's effects on various organs such as the lungs, skin, brain, and reproductive system, but there is limited direct evidence regarding its role as a thyroid disrupting chemical. Research has shown that paraquat can be absorbed through the skin in humans, albeit minimally ([Wester et al., 1984](#)), and it has neurotoxic effects when injected into the brain of experimental animals ([Corasaniti et al., 1998](#)). Additionally, paraquat exposure has been linked to significant damage to epididymal sperm in mice, affecting sperm count and motility ([Ashoka et al., 2013](#)). Furthermore, oral administration of paraquat in rats resulted in lung damage as the primary target organ, with subsequent effects on the heart, liver, and kidneys ([Studies on Pararquat toxicity \(1\), n.d.](#)).

In the developing cerebellum, thyroid hormones deficiency during the perinatal period caused growth reduction and, decrement in synapses of Purkinje cells, ramification of Purkinje cell dendrites, and retardation of granule cell proliferation, migration, and development ([Tsatsakis et al., 1996](#); [Kimura et al., 2002](#); [Koibuchi et al., 2000](#); [Farwell et al., 2005](#)). Therefore, the observed biochemical alterations in excitatory neurotransmitter levels during mouse cerebellar cortex synaptogenesis indicated the toxic effects of oxidative stress as well as possible hypofunction of the thyroid gland that could have been caused by the chronic exposure to PQ during its formation period ([Miranda et al.,](#)

[2005](#)).

3. Glyphosate

Glyphosate (G), a broad-spectrum herbicide, is an organophosphate (OP) compound used worldwide. It binds and competitively inhibits the activity of enolpyruvylshikimate-3-phosphate synthase (EPSPS) of plants and micro-organisms, an enzyme involved in the shikimic acid pathway ([Amrhein et al., 1980](#); [Herrmann et al., 1999](#)). Glyphosate usage has increased extensively since Monsanto introduced glyphosate-tolerant crop varieties in 1996 (namely, sugar beet, maize, alfalfa, canola, cotton, etc.) to be used in along with Roundup, the glyphosate-based herbicide (GBH) ([Benbrook, 2016](#)). The median half-life (TH) of glyphosates in the field is reportedly 47 days and the primary breakdown products are aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA) and glyoxylate ([Vencill, 2002](#)).

A. Epidemiological evidence

A prospective cohort study of licensed pesticide applicators with 35,150 male and female participants in North Carolina and Iowa demonstrated that self-reported use of glyphosate was associated with an increased risk of hypothyroidism ([Shrestha et al., 2018](#)). However, these findings contradicted with results obtained from the same cohort study conducted by [Goldner et al., \(2013\)](#) and [Lerro et al., \(2018\)](#).

B. In vivo evidence

[IARC \(2015\)](#) reviewed ten rodent bioassays and reported on five tumours in three of these bioassays that were interpreted as showing evidence of carcinogenicity: A positive dose-response trend was reported for thyroid C-cell adenoma in female rats (2/60, 2/60, 6/60, 6/60, p = 0.031) ([Stout and Ruecker 1990](#)). In humans, [Samsel et al., \(2013\)](#) hypothesized that glyphosate intake could interfere with selenium uptake, impacting thyroid hormone synthesis, and increasing thyroid cancer risks.

In in vivo studies evaluating glyphosate as a thyroid-disrupting chemical, research has shown conflicting results. While some studies suggest that glyphosate does not interact with the estrogen, androgen, and thyroid (EAT) hormone pathways, including steroidogenesis, based on in vitro and in vivo Tier 1 assays and comprehensive toxicology databases ([Levine et al., 2020](#)), other studies indicate that glyphosate-based herbicides can act as intergenerational endocrine disruptors affecting thyroid homeostasis in cerebellar cells, leading to altered gene expression and epigenetic changes in offspring exposed during the perinatal phase ([Costa Reis et al., 2021](#)). Additionally, in vitro studies on human thyroid-derived cell lines have demonstrated a non-monotonic dose-response curve, with low concentrations of glyphosate-based herbicides causing both cell death and proliferation, especially in cancerous thyroid cells, suggesting a potential role in the increased incidence of thyroid nodules and cancer observed globally ([Dal et al., 2022](#)).

Surprisingly, few studies retrieved were discovered to be relevant to glyphosate/GBH exposure and thyroid endpoints. In a first in vivo study, four different North American amphibian species (*Rana clamitans*, *Rana pipiens*, *R. sylvatica*, and *Bufo americanus*) exposed to glyphosate and the surfactant polyethoxylated tallowamine (POEA), and six different glyphosate-based formulations. The time to metamorphosis and expression of *thrb* were measured to investigate HPT axis disruption. Glyphosate alone and formulations lacking POEA were found to be the least toxic, however *R. pipiens* tadpoles after exposure to either POEA or glyphosate formulations containing POEA showed delayed metamorphosis and decreased snout-vent length at the peak of metamorphosis after exposure to either POEA or glyphosate formulations containing POEA. These effects may be associated with the enhanced *thrb* mRNA levels observed in the same exposure conditions. This study indicates the need for surfactant composition to be taken into consideration in the evaluation of risk assessment of GBH (Howe et al., 2004). In the second in vivo study, female pregnant Wistar rats were exposed to either 5 or 50 mg/kg BW/day Roundup® Transorb (Monsanto) from gestation day 18 (GD 18) to postnatal day 5 (PND 5). For hormonal, metabolomics, or gene expression analysis at PND 90, Blood and tissue samples from the heart, liver, pituitary, and hypothalamus were collected. In every tissue collected, TH-related genes (hypothalamus genes encoding deiodinases 2 (Dio2) and 3 (Dio3) and TH transporters *Slc1c1* (former *Oatp1c1*) and *Slc16a2* (former *Mct8*) gene expression reduced; pituitary Dio2, thyroid hormone receptor genes (*Thra1* and *Thrb1*) expression elevated; Liver *Thra1* and *Thrb1* showed enhanced mRNA expression; and *Slc16a2*, *Mb*, *Myh6* (former *Mhca*) and *Slc2a4* (former *Glut4*) of heart showed higher degree of expression and *Tshb* gene with no change between groups) were observed to be differentially expressed in exposure groups compared to the control group. Levels of TSH were diminished in exposure groups, however levels of both T3 and T4 were unaffected. This inquisitive absence of TH hormone effects, despite TSH and target gene changes, may reflect changes in TSH set-point resulting from differential gene programming in rats during the fetal period (de Souza et al., 2017). In another frog investigation (*Lithobates sylvaticus*), glyphosate-formulated exposure alters brain gene expression for *thrb* and Dio3 enzyme, with different alterations relying upon the stage (Leemans et al., 2019). Studies with amphibians demonstrated that glyphosate interferes with thyroid hormone signalling through elevation of thyroid hormone receptor- β (Navarro-Martín et al., 2014).

In another study by Latifa et al., (2020), female Wistar rats were exposed to Kalach 360 SL (KL), a GBH (doses were 126 mg of G/Kg, and 315 mg of G/Kg). This KL exposure induced a perturbation of bone metabolism (calcium and phosphorus) and hormonal status disturbance. The

histological and immunohistochemical study of the thyroid gland revealed a disturbance in morphological structure and thyroid cell function and resulted in hypothyroidism. KL induced an increment of the thyroids appearance relating to the follicles in rest, along with a decrease of the number of the active follicles; in addition to the appearance of the macrophage, dilated follicle, and flattened epithelium, the histomorphometric study showed a reduction in colloid volume (48 % and 55.5 %) (Latifa et al., 2020). Zhang et al., (2021) also confirmed glyphosate mediated hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid (HPT) axis disruption by examining the expression levels of genes related to the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid (HPT) axis. In their study, the relative expression levels of both *Dio2* and *Mct8* genes decreased in the hypothalamus from G-treated mice. In pituitary tissue, *Dio2*, *Mct8* and *Trhr* genes expression in Glyphosate groups significantly increased ($p < 0.01$) compared with the control group. The expression of related genes (*Nis*, *Tpo*, *Tg*, *Tshr*) in thyroid tissue reduced significantly reflecting the study conducted by de Souza et al., (2017). Recently, de Souza et al., (2021) have evaluated the effect of glyphosate-based herbicides (GBH) as an intergenerational endocrine disrupter on thyroid homeostasis in cerebellar cells. In their study, female pregnant Wistar rats were exposed to Roundup Transorb® solution at 5 and 50 mg/kg/day, from gestation day 18 (GD18) to postnatal day 5 (PND5). The cerebellum of male offspring was utilized to assess the gene expression. Results indicate that animals exposed to non-toxic GBH doses during the perinatal stage convey intergenerational alterations in key regulators of cellular thyroid hormone homeostasis and epigenetic controllers in adulthood, indicating the conceivable ED effect of GBH based on epigenetic alterations (de Souza et al., 2021).

4. Atrazine

Atrazine (6-chloro-N-ethyl-N'-(1-methylethyl)-1, 3, 5-triazine-2, 4-diamine) is a triazine herbicide widely used in the United States. Atrazine leaching from the soil to surface water is estimated at 1% per year (Goolsby et al., 1993) and may be transported to areas as far as 1,000 km from the site of utilization by means of atmospheric transport and deposition through precipitation (Wan, 2015). Several studies have suggested that atrazine is an endocrine disruptor in various species, including amphibians, fish, and exposure levels were high in birds and rodents (Hayes, 2011). The International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) records atrazine as not classifiable as to its carcinogenicity to humans (Group 3).

Studies examining the effects of atrazine on metamorphosis suggests no consistent concentration-related effect on thyroid function (Solomon et al., 2008). Several studies have reported no effect of ATR on the time to metamorphosis in *X. laevis* or *R. pipiens* (Solomon et al., 2008). When female Wistar rat were exposed to 200 mg/kg atrazine (ATR), the

serum T3, T4, and TSH levels were unaltered and no histopathological/ morphologic changes in the thyroid gland were observed ([Law et al., 2000](#)).

Stoker et al., (2000) when exposed male Wister rat to 200 mg/kg ATR, no difference was observed in the TSH, and T4 level, however, T3 level was elevated. In the subsequent study with ATR- metabolites, TSH, T3, and T4 were unaffected. Also, no effects on the thyroid histology were observed ([Stoker et al., 2002](#)).

Conclusion

In vitro study is lacking to understand the effect of these herbicides. Also, (i) experiments should be designed to understand the gender specificity, and (ii) how different concentration and levels of herbicides affects differently has not yet fully understood. This review suggests that an environmentally relevant dose of herbicides exposure to the thyroid gland may have risk factors to develop thyroid disorders. The risks were highest for hypothyroidism in the general population exposed to herbicides. However, other thyroid diseases associated with herbicides exposure are less understood. Therefore, future studies are essential in this area to bridge the knowledge gap.

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